

MARKETING AUTHORIZATION OF PHARMACEUTICALS IN UNITED STATES (US), EUROPEAN UNION (EU) AND INDIA

Imran A. W. Sheikh*, Neha V. Ramteke, Jayprakash N. Gayakwad, Rutuja A. Dhore, Nishant D. Anelkar, Dr. Ajay G. Pise

Department of Pharmaceutical Regulatory Affairs, Dadasaheb Balpande College of Pharmacy, Besa, Nagpur, 440037, Maharashtra.

Article Received on 28 April 2026,
Article Revised on 18 May 2026,
Article Published on 01 June 2026

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20443645>

*Corresponding Author

Imran A. W. Sheikh

Department of Pharmaceutical
Regulatory Affairs, Dadasaheb
Balpande College of Pharmacy, Besa,
Nagpur, 440037, Maharashtra.

How To Cite This Article: Imran A. W. Sheikh*, Neha V. Ramteke, Jayprakash N. Gayakwad, Rutuja A. Dhore, Nishant D. Anelkar, Dr. Ajay G. Pise. (2026). Marketing Authorization of Pharmaceuticals in United States (US), European Union (EU) And India. World Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Sciences, 15(6), 788–806.

this work is licensed under Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International license.

ABSTRACT

Marketing authorization is a regulatory process that ensures pharmaceutical products meet standards of safety, efficacy, and quality before market entry. This article compares the marketing authorization procedures in the United States, European Union, and India. The United States follows IND and NDA/ANDA pathways regulated by the FDA, while the European Union provides centralized, decentralized, mutual recognition, and national procedures coordinated by the EMA. In India, approvals are granted by CDSCO/DCGI under the Drugs and Cosmetics Act, 1940, based on clinical and non-clinical data submission. Despite differences in regulatory frameworks, all regions require CTD/eCTD dossier submission and emphasize clinical evaluation and post-marketing surveillance. Understanding these procedures helps in developing effective global regulatory strategies and facilitating timely drug approvals across major markets.

KEYWORDS: Marketing Authorization, Investigational New Drug, New Drug Application, Centralized Procedure, Decentralized Procedure, Mutual Recognition Procedure, Drug and Cosmetics act 1940, Clinical Trails, Drug Development, USFDA, EMA, CDSCO.

INTRODUCTION

Marketing Authorization

Marketing Authorization (MA) is the official approval granted by a regulatory authority (like the FDA or EMA) that allows a pharmaceutical company to sell, market, and distribute a specific medicinal product, confirming it meets stringent criteria for safety, efficacy, and quality after rigorous scientific review of submitted data.

In order to authorize the new medicine in the respective countries, all nations must follow the regulatory standards. The most difficult aspect is developing a consistent regulatory approach for Marketing Authorization Applications (MAA) across many countries. Thus, it is critical to understand the regulatory requirements for MAA in each nation. Each country has its own regulatory requirements that must be completed before a new pharmaceutical may be licensed there. It is difficult to apply a single regulatory strategy for the approval of a new treatment in many countries. Many corporations concentrate on their regulatory frameworks in this industry since it is widely acknowledged that the United States (US) and the European Union (EU) are the two most promising markets in the world for pharmaceutical products.^[1,2]

Figure: Flow of Marketing Application.

MARKETING AUTHORIZATION PROCEDURE FOR PHARMACEUTICALS IN UNITED STATES (US)

The United States may have the strictest requirements in the world for authorizing new drugs. Many people believe that American drug approval criteria are the most stringent in the world. The formation of the United States Pharmacopoeia in 1820 signalled a new era in American drug control. In 1906, Congress passed the first Food and medication Act, which established legal requirements for medication potency and purity. The sulphanilamide tragedy in 1937 prompted the passage of the Federal Food, Drug, and Cosmetic Act (of 1938), which established new laws requiring new medications to be proven safe before being commercialized. The Food and Drug Administration (FDA) is responsible for protecting and

improving societal wellbeing. The FDA's new drug approval process, which is comparable to that for generic medications, consists of two steps: clinical trials (CT) and new drug application (NDA) approval. A novel drug application (NDA) governs the new drug product (NDP). These applications are accepted in eCTD format for assessment. The NDA's major focus is on the product's effectiveness and safety. Only when an investigational new drug (IND) application is filed to the FDA.^[1,2]

Figure: Drug Approval Process in US.

Investigational New Drug (IND)

An IND (Investigational New Drug) is a formal request to the U.S. Food and Drug Administration (FDA) to administer an experimental drug or biological product in human clinical trials, allowing sponsors to ship it across state lines for investigation before marketing approval, ensuring it meets safety and quality standards.^[1,3]

Types of INDs

Investigational IND: An Investigational IND is submitted by a physician who also oversees the administration or distribution of the experimental medicine, as well as the planning, organization, and execution of the research. A physician may submit a research IND to investigate an approved pharmaceutical, an unapproved medicine, or both for a new indication or in a new patient population.

Emergency IND: If there isn't enough time to submit an IND, the FDA can use this to approve the use of an investigational drug.

Treatment IND: While the FDA inquiry is ongoing, it is filed for experimental medications that have shown promise in clinical studies for severe or urgently life-threatening diseases.^[4] The two categories of INDs are commercial and research (non-commercial). The IND application must include information from the following three broad areas.

Animal pharmacology and toxicology investigations: Preclinical data are used to determine if the product is sufficiently safe for beginning human testing. Any prior human experience with the medicine (typically from another country) is also considered.

Manufacturing data: Information about the composition, manufacturer, stability, and manufacturing controls for the drug substance and drug product. This information is reviewed to ensure that the firm can make and distribute consistent batches of the medicine.

Clinical protocol and investigators information: Detailed protocols for proposed clinical investigations to determine if the preliminary trials would subject individuals to undue risks. Also included is information on the credentials of clinical investigators--professionals (usually physicians) who supervise the administration of the experimental compound--to determine if they are qualified to perform their clinical trial tasks. Finally, pledges to get informed permission from research subjects, have the study reviewed by an institutional review board (IRB), and follow the investigational new drug laws.

The sponsor must wait 30 calendar days after submitting the IND to begin any clinical studies. During this time, the FDA can review the IND to verify that research participants are not exposed to an unreasonable level of risk.^[2,3]

Figure: Flowchart of IND Filing.

New Drug Application (NDA)

The New Drug Application (NDA) serves as the foundation for rules and oversight over new pharmaceuticals. Every new medicine has been subject to an authorized NDA. The NDA application is submitted to the FDA by drug sponsors and is the vehicle by which the FDA authorizes a novel pharmaceutical for sale and marketing in the United States. The NDA includes the Investigational new Drug (IND).^[2,5]

The NDA includes the following information for submission to the FDA reviewer

- Drug's activities throughout clinical trials
- Drug Ingredients
- Results of animal studies
- Safety and efficacy of drugs in the human body.
- Risk/benefit ratio
- Drug's identity, strength, quality, and purity.
- Production, processing, labelling, and packaging of drugs

The NDA's aims are to offer enough material for FDA reviewers to make the following essential decisions

1. Whether the medicine is safe and effective in its intended application(s), and whether the benefits exceed the dangers.
2. Determine if the drug's proposed labelling (package insert) is suitable and what it should include.
3. Whether the drug's production processes and quality control measures are sufficient to maintain the drug's identity, strength, quality, and purity.^[1,5]

To obtain permission to commercialize a novel drug in the United States, a new drug Application must be submitted. The NDA includes both the data from the IND and the results of clinical studies that demonstrate efficacy and safety. After receiving an NDA, the FDA must start the review process within 60 days.^[5]

The application comes in two copies

Archival copy: It contains copies of tabulations and clinical study case report forms that FDA reviewers can use as a reference tool to locate material that was not included in the review copy.

Review copy: Each folder has a unique binding for each technical element.^[2,5]

Figure: Flow process of NDA Filing.

Abbreviated New Drug Application (ANDA)

An abbreviated new drug application (ANDA) comprises information that is submitted to the FDA for assessment and possible approval of a generic drug product. Once authorized, an application may produce and promote the generic drug product as a safe, effective, and less expensive alternative to the brand-name medicine it references.^[1,6]

A generic drug product is one that is similar to an innovator drug product in terms of dosage form, strength, method of administration, quality, performance properties, and intended application. The FDA's authorized Drug medications with Therapeutic Equivalence Evaluations (Orange Book) contains a list of all authorized medications, innovator and generic.^[6]

Generic drug applications are referred to as "abbreviated" since they are not needed to contain preclinical (animal) and clinical (human) evidence to demonstrate safety and efficacy. Instead, generic applicants must scientifically prove that their product works in the same way as the original medication. Applicants can establish that a generic product operates similarly to the innovator medicine by measuring the time it takes for the generic drug to enter the bloodstream in healthy volunteers. This evidence of "bioequivalence" provides the rate of absorption, or bioavailability, of the generic medicine, which may then be compared to the innovator drug. To be authorized by the FDA, the generic version must deliver the same quantity of active chemicals into a patient's circulation in the same time frame as the innovator medicine.^[2,6]

The "Drug Price Competition and Patent Term Restoration Act of 1984," commonly known as the Hatch-Waxman Amendments, established bioequivalence as the standard for licensing generic drug products. These Amendments allow the FDA to approve applications to launch generic copies of brand-name medications without the need for costly and duplicative clinical trials to show safety and effectiveness. The Hatch-Waxman Amendments provided brand-name firms with patent term extensions to account for the time the patented product is being reviewed by the FDA, as well as specific periods of commercial exclusivity. In addition to the ANDA approval procedure, generic medicine businesses now have the right to challenge patents in court before marketing, as well as 180 days of generic medication exclusivity.^[2,6]

Figure: Flow process of ANDA.

MARKETING AUTHORIZATION PROCEDURE FOR PHARMACEUTICALS IN EUROPEAN UNION (EU)

The European Medicines Agency (EMA) was established in London in 1995 to coordinate the review and monitoring of drugs for both human and veterinary use by member states of the European Union (EU). It outlined a systematic method for developing, reviewing, approving, and implementing pharmaceutical recommendations. In European countries, the approval procedure for pharmaceuticals is done in two stages.

- Clinical Trials Application
- Marketing Authorization Application.^[1,2]

The state's relevant authority receives a clinical trial application (CTA), which must be lodged in order to undertake clinical research in the European Union. The application is reviewed by the member state's competent authorities. Clinical research is conducted only with consent. Only after successfully completing all three clinical trial phases is a marketing authorization application submitted.

The following volumes, whose titles are The Rules Governing Medicinal Products in the European Union, include the European Law including the pharmaceutical directives.

Table: Volumes of EUDRALEX.^[7]

Volume 1	Pharmaceutical Laws for Human Use Medicinal Products.
Volume 2	Notice to Applicants for Human Medicinal Product.
Volume 3	Scientific Recommendations for Human Medicinal Products.
Volume 4	GMP Guidelines for Pharmaceuticals for Human and Animal Use.
Volume 5	Pharmaceutical Regulations for Veterinary Pharmaceuticals.
Volume 6	Notice to Applicants for Veterinary Medicine Products.
Volume 7	Scientific Recommendations for Veterinary Pharmaceuticals.
Volume 8	Limits on Maximum Residue.
Volume 9	Pharmacovigilance Recommendations for Drugs Used in Human and Veterinary Medicine.
Volume 10	Guidelines for clinical trials.

Medicines are market authorized through a range of administrative processes and organizational structures across Europe. The European Union has four options for gaining marketing permission for pharmaceuticals.

Figure: Marketing Authorization procedures in European Union.

Centralized Procedure

Centralized processes are required for

1. Drugs produced using any technological procedure, such as genetic engineering.
2. Drugs used to treat autoimmune illnesses, diabetes, cancer, HIV/AIDS, neurological disorders.
3. Drugs used to treat uncommon disorders that have been formally categorized as "orphan medicines".^[7,8]

In the Centralized Procedure, the applicant applies to the EMEA for marketing permission and obtains a single European approval that is applicable in all 27 member countries, as well as Norway, Iceland, and Liechtenstein. At least seven months before submission, the applicant must notify the EMEA of their plan to submit an application. Applicants can meet with the EMEA before submitting their applications to resolve any procedural or regulatory difficulties. The applicant's request for eligibility for assessment under the Centralized Procedure, along with a reason and supporting papers, is provided to all CHMP (Committee for Medicinal Product for Human Use) members. Following debate at CHMP, the EMEA notifies the applicant of the CHMP position whether the medical product is eligible for assessment under the Centralized Procedure.^[8]

Figure: Centralized Procedure.

For every scientific examination, a Rapporteur and, if applicable, a Co-Rapporteur are selected from among the CHMP members. The Rapporteur's job is to conduct the scientific review and provide an Assessment Report for the CHMP in accordance with the timeframe

established for the evaluation procedure. Where needed, the Rapporteur may be assisted by a Co-Rapporteur, who provides a separate complete Assessment Report or a criticism of the Rapporteur's report at the discretion of the CHMP.

Once the application is checked and found complete, and the Rapporteur and Co-Rapporteur confirm they have the dossier, the EMEA starts the process on the first day of the month listed on their website. The Rapporteur and Co-Rapporteur send their first assessment reports to the CHMP members and EMEA by Day 80. The CHMP members then review the scientific work done by the Rapporteur and Co-Rapporteur, as well as check if their scientific and regulatory conclusions are correct. On Day 120, the CHMP sends the List of Questions, along with their overall conclusions and a review of the scientific data, to the applicant. The EMEA pauses the timeline so the applicant can prepare a response. Once the applicant sends their responses, the CHMP creates a schedule for evaluating those responses. The EMEA makes sure the CHMP's opinion is given within 90 more days. After the CHMP gives a positive opinion, the applicant provides the EMEA with the final translated versions of all necessary documents in every EU language, including Norwegian. Within 30 days, the EMEA sends the CHMP opinion and other needed documents to the European Commission, the Standing Committee members, Norway, and Iceland. The European Commission then grants the marketing authorization, which is valid across the whole EU and gives the same rights and responsibilities in each country as if it had been approved nationally. The European Public Assessment Report (EPAR) is published on the EMEA website once the Commission has made its decision.^[8]

Decentralized Procedure

The new DCP took effect in the EU in 2005. The goal of this method is to get marketing authorizations in several Member States when none have been obtained inside the European Community. The applicant should submit an application to the relevant authorities in each Member State where they intend to receive a marketing license. The applicant may nominate a nation to serve as the Reference Member State (RMS). Many factors influence the RMS selection process, including workload, past experience, hobbies, and the RMS's approval of the dossier.^[8,9]

Figure: Decentralized Procedure.

The RMS will begin the procedure after the application has been found to be complete by both the RMS and all CMS(s). Within 70 days, the RMS provides the CMS(s) and the applicant with a preliminary assessment report on the dossier. The CMS(s) is requested to comment on the proposed national prescription status and notify the RMS. On day 105, the RMS will convey any comments to the applicant and, if required, suspend the clock until the applicant has completed a response document. On day 120, the RMS writes a Draft Assessment Report and may conclude the procedure if the CMS(s) and the RMS agrees. Otherwise, the CMS(s) have 90 days to approve the Draft Assessment Report and related papers. Competent authorities of the RMS and CMS(s) make a decision within 30 days after acknowledging their assent to the Assessment Report and accompanying documentation. A national marketing permission will be given in the RMS and each CMS(s) following a favourable agreement at the completion of the Decentralized Procedure.^[8,9]

Mutual Recognition Procedure

The MRP has been in effect in the EU since 1995. The goal of this method is to secure marketing authorizations in one or more Member States once the pharmaceutical product has previously been approved by at least one nation in the European Community. In this scenario, the applicant requests that one or more CMS(s) mutually acknowledge the authority issued by the RMS. If the RMS marketing permission is based on an obsolete dossier format, the dossiers must be reformatted before the MRP begins.^[8,10]

Figure: Mutual Recognition Procedure.

The holder of a marketing authorization must submit an application to the RMS's and CMS's respective competent authorities. Within 90 days after receiving a valid application, the RMS provides the Assessment Report, or amends any existing one as needed, and sends it to the CMS(s) and the applicant, together with additional documentation. The clock starts when the RMS receives the Assessment Report and each CMS(s) validates the application. Within 90 days, the CMS(s) recognize the RMS's judgment. Thirty days after the procedure concludes, the CMS(s) competent authority make a decision and award marketing permission. As a result, if the MRP concludes successfully, a national marketing license will be awarded in each of the CMS(s).^[8,10]

Nationalized Procedure

Every country in Europe has its own regulatory organization. National procedure refers to a collection of norms that each country has implemented. Even the smallest firms can pay the expenditures. The cost of translating into English or another regional language is decreased. It establishes the basis for mutual recognition. The National Procedure cannot be used to register biotechnology methods. Centralized filing through EMA is essential. Marketing clearance is granted upon assessment of the application submitted by the sponsor to the national competent body in line with national rules.^[8]

Figure: Nationalized Procedure.

MARKETING AUTHORIZATION PROCEDURE FOR PHARMACEUTICALS IN INDIA

The Indian Parliament enacted the Drug and Cosmetic Act of 1940 along with the Rules of 1945 to regulate the import, production, distribution, and sale of medicines and cosmetics. As a result, the Central Drugs Standard Control Organization (CDSCO) and the Office of the Drugs Controller General (DCGI) were set up. In 1988, the Indian government updated the Drug and Cosmetics Rules of 1945 by adding Schedule Y. This schedule includes the standards and guidelines for conducting clinical investigations. In order to get permission from the licensing authority, which is the DCGI, a company in India must fill out Form 44 and provide all the required information as specified in Schedule Y of the Drugs and Cosmetics Act 1940 and Rules 1945. Clinical studies must follow the guidelines in Schedule Y, and the results must be properly submitted to show that the drug is effective and safe for the Indian population.^[2,11]

RULES

Section 122A of the Drug and Cosmetics Act exempts new drugs from clinical research requirements if they have been approved and used for a number of years in other nations. According to Section 2.4 (a) of Schedule Y's Drugs and Cosmetics Act of 1940 and Rules of 1945, medicinal compounds developed in India must undergo all stages of clinical trials.

According to Section 2.4(b) of Schedule Y of the Drugs and Cosmetics Act 1940 and Rules 1945, applicants who discover drug substances in countries other than India are required to provide data from those countries. The licensing authority has the option to ask them to reconduct all the studies or allow them to proceed to Phase III clinical trials. Before getting a license from the Central Drug Standard Control Organization (CDSCO) for importing or developing new medicines, the drug product must show that it is safe and effective for human use. The information needed to approve an application for importing or creating a new medicine for commercial use is given in the Drugs and Cosmetics Act of 1940 and its regulations 1945, 122A, 122B, and 122D. The sponsor must provide the Drug Controller General of India (DCGI) with complete details on the following for an experimental new medicine.^[1,11]

1. Generic name
2. Patent status
3. Brief description of physiochemical/ biological

4. Technical information
 - Stability
 - Specification
 - Manufacturing process
 - Worldwide regulatory status
5. Published Clinical trial Report
6. Proposed protocol and pro format
7. Trial Duration
8. Drug Master File
9. Undertaking to Report Serious or Life-threatening Adverse drug reaction.

Depending on how well a drug is accepted in other countries, it might be necessary to conduct regional clinical trials in India. Usually, Phase III studies are required when a medicine has already been approved in another country. India does not allow Phase I trials unless there is supporting data from other nations. However, Phase I studies can be conducted in India if the drug has a special link to a disease that affects Indians, like tuberculosis or malaria. Bioavailability and bioequivalence (BA/BE) studies should be done following BA/BE guidelines. It is also necessary to provide complete information about the drug's marketing status in other countries, along with details on its safety and effectiveness. This includes prescription information, samples, testing procedures, product monographs, and labels. A clinical study is typically approved in India after 3 months. When registering clinical studies with the Clinical Trials Registry of India (CTRI), information about participants and the trial must be provided. The rules that must be followed under Drugs and Cosmetics Rules 1945 are

Rule 122 - A: Request for authorization to import a new drug

Rule 122 - B: Request for authorization to produce new medications not listed in Schedules C and C (1)

Rule 122 - D: Authorization to produce or import a fixed-dose combination

Rule 122 - DA: Request for authorization to conduct clinical studies for experimental or new drugs

Rule 122 - DAB: Compensation in case of injury or death during clinical trials.^[1,11]

STAGES OF DRUG APPROVAL IN INDIA

Figure: Drug approval process in India.

COMPARISON OF MA PROCEDURES IN US, EU & INDIA

Parameter	United States (US)	European Union (EU)	India
Regulatory Authority	Food and Drug Administration (FDA)	European Medicines Agency (EMA) & National Competent Authorities	Central Drugs Standard Control Organization (CDSCO), DCGI
Governing Law	Federal Food, Drug and Cosmetic Act	EU Directives and EudraLex	Drugs and Cosmetics Act 1940 & Rules 1945
Application Type	IND → NDA (Innovator) ANDA (Generic)	CTA → MAA	Form 44 for New Drug Approval
Pre-Clinical Requirement	Required before IND submission	Required before CTA submission	Required as per Schedule Y
Clinical Trial Authorization	Investigational New Drug (IND)	Clinical Trial Application (CTA)	Clinical Trial Permission (Rule 122DA)
Clinical Trial Phases	Phase I, II, III	Phase I, II, III	Phase I, II, III (may waive Phase I for foreign drugs)
Marketing Application	New Drug Application (NDA)	Marketing Authorization Application (MAA)	New Drug Approval Application to DCGI
Generic Drug Approval	ANDA (Bioequivalence based)	Hybrid/Generic Application	BA/BE Study submission
Approval Pathways	Single centralized FDA approval	Centralized, Decentralized, Mutual Recognition, National	Single national procedure

Review Format	eCTD	eCTD	eCTD (now mandatory)
Review Timeline	~10–12 months (standard)	~210 days (Centralized procedure)	~6–12 months (varies)
Market Authorization Validity	No fixed validity (post-approval monitoring)	5 years (renewable)	Typically perpetual after approval
Clinical Trial Registration	ClinicalTrials.gov	EU Clinical Trial Register	CTRI (Clinical Trial Registry of India)
Regulatory Focus	Safety, efficacy, quality	Benefit-risk evaluation	Safety, efficacy in Indian population
Approval Scope	United States only	All EU member states (Centralized)	India only
Language Requirement	English	Multiple EU languages	English
Dossier Format	CTD / eCTD	CTD / eCTD	CTD / eCTD
Post Marketing Surveillance	Phase IV, REMS	Pharmacovigilance (EudraVigilance)	Pharmacovigilance Programme of India (PvPI)

CONCLUSION

The marketing authorization procedures in the United States, European Union, and India are designed to ensure the safety, efficacy, and quality of pharmaceutical products before market entry, although their regulatory frameworks differ. The United States follows a stringent pathway involving IND and NDA/ANDA submissions, while the European Union provides multiple approval routes such as centralized, decentralized, mutual recognition, and national procedures. In contrast, India follows a national approval system regulated by CDSCO and DCGI, with requirements based on the Drugs and Cosmetics Act and Schedule Y.

Despite these differences, all regions require comprehensive clinical, non-clinical, and quality data in CTD/eCTD format and emphasize post-marketing surveillance. Understanding these regulatory variations is important for developing effective global marketing authorization strategies and facilitating timely approval across different markets.

REFERENCES

1. Modi K, Patel P, Parmar K. Drug approval process in US, Europe, India, and Canada. *Int. J. Biol. Pharm. Allied. Sci.*, 2024; 13(9). doi:10.31032/ijbpas/2024/13.9.8300.
2. Sawant AM, Mali DP, Bhagwat DA. Regulatory requirements and drug approval process in India, Europe and US. *Pharm. Regul. Aff.*, 2018; 7: 210. doi:10.4172/2167-7689.1000210.

3. U.S. Food and Drug Administration. Investigational New Drug (IND) Application [Internet]. Silver Spring (MD): FDA; [cited 2026 Mar 31]. Available from: <https://www.fda.gov/drugs/types-applications/investigational-new-drug-ind-application>
4. Electronic Code of Federal Regulations (eCFR). Part 312—Investigational new drug application [Internet]. Washington (DC): National Archives; [cited 2026 Mar 31]. Available from: <https://www.ecfr.gov/current/title-21/chapter-I/subchapter-D/part-312>
5. U.S. Food and Drug Administration. New drug application (NDA) [Internet]. Silver Spring (MD): FDA; [cited 2026 Mar 31]. Available from: <https://www.fda.gov/drugs/types-applications/new-drug-application-nda>
6. U.S. Food and Drug Administration. Abbreviated new drug application (ANDA) [Internet]. Silver Spring (MD): FDA; [cited 2026 Mar 31]. Available from: <https://www.fda.gov/drugs/types-applications/abbreviated-new-drug-application-anda>
7. European Parliament and Council of the European Union. Directive 2001/83/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 6 November 2001 on the community code relating to medicinal products for human use [Internet]. Official Journal of the European Communities. 2001; L311: 67-128. Available from: [+https://www.ema.europa.eu/en/documents/regulatory-procedural-guideline/directive-200183ec-european-parliament-and-council-6-november-2001-community-code-relating-medicinal-products-human-use_en.pdf](https://www.ema.europa.eu/en/documents/regulatory-procedural-guideline/directive-200183ec-european-parliament-and-council-6-november-2001-community-code-relating-medicinal-products-human-use_en.pdf)
8. GS Life Science Services. Clinical marketing authorization procedures [Internet]. Geneva: SGS; [cited 2026 Mar 31]. Available from: <https://www.sgs.com/fr/-/media/sgscorp/documents/corporate/brochures/sgs-clinical-marketing-authorization-en-09.cdn.en.pdf>
9. Chakraborty R, Yadav K. Drug approval process in US, Europe, and India and its regulatory requirements: a review. 2018; 6: 31-39.
10. Mahapatra AK, Sameeraja NH, Murthy PN. Drug approval process in United States of America, European Union and India: a review. *Acrc. Tra.*, 2014; 1: 13-22
11. Gupta NV, Reddy CM, Reddy KP, Kulkarni RA, Shivakumar S, et al. Process of approval of new drug in India with emphasis on clinical trials. 2012; 13: 17-23.